

Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper. Part III. Copper-Lactate-Aminocarboxylate Complexes

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Formation and stability of mixed-ligand complexes of Cu^{2+} with lactic acid as primary ligand and some amino acids as secondary ligands were determined by *pH*-metry and by spectrophotometry at 30° and at $\mu=0.25$ (KNO_3). $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ values indicate the favoured formation of these mixed-ligand complexes with heterodonor atoms when compared to mixed-ligand complexes with identical donor atoms. The factors affecting the formation and stability of the mixed-ligand complexes are discussed.

THE increasing number of studies on formation of mixed-ligand complexes reveals a realisation of their growing importance, particularly in their role in biological processes. The formation of such complexes is a general feature of systems where a metal is present with two or more ligands. An analysis of the formation constant data on these complexes shows that their formation is a favoured process over that of simple complexes. A survey of the literature shows that studies undertaken involve mostly complexes formed by amines and amino acids and to some extent, phenols and phenolic acids¹⁻⁴. Study of complexes involving aliphatic hydroxy acids should provide interesting information since the hydroxo group is weak in its tendency to co-ordination^{5,6}. Weak bonding by OH groups of glycollic, lactic and some hydroxy amino acids present in biological systems is believed to aid enzyme catalysis. Study of mixed-ligand formation with lactic acid as one of the ligands was undertaken as part of a systematic study involving hydroxy acids.

The present work reports the study of the formation of ternary complexes of copper with lactic acid and aminocarboxylic acids by spectrophotometry. The results obtained have been checked by *pH* metric studies.

Experimental

Reagents: All reagents used were from standard manufacturers and of high purity. All the solutions are made in double distilled water and estimated by standard procedures.

Measurements:

(i) *pH*-metry: The titrations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere in the solutions at constant ionic strength, $\mu=0.25$ (KNO_3) in a thermostatted bath at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. A digital *pH* meter

(ECIL, *pH* 822A, accuracy ± 0.01 *pH* unit) was used to measure the *pH*. The instrument was calibrated before each titration with $0.05M$ potassium hydrogen phthalate, *pH* 4.01 at 30° .

Absorbance Measurements: The absorbance measurements were made with a Carl Zeiss single beam spectrophotometer, model VSU-2P, with matched 1 cm glass cells. Here also the measurements were made at $\mu=0.25$ (KNO_3) and the cells were thermostatted at $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Ionisation Constants of the Ligands: The ionisation constant of lactic acid was determined under our laboratory conditions by the method of Albert and Sergeant⁷. The ionisation constants for other ligands were taken from our earlier work⁸.

Formation Constant of the Binary Complexes: The formation constants of all amino acids were taken from our earlier work⁸. The values for lactic acid were taken from literature⁹.

Formation Constants of the Mixed-ligand Complexes (*pH*-metry):

The formation of the mixed-ligand complexes were studied under the same conditions for binary complexes, except that the solutions contained both ligands. In solutions containing equal amounts of lactic acid and amino acid, hydrolysis starts even at low *pH*s. Calculations yielded good results when lactic acid and amino acid are present in the ratio of 4 : 1.

Spectrophotometry: Absorbance measurements were made with solutions containing a fixed amount of Copper(II) and varying amounts of the two ligands—always keeping the total concentration of the two ligands many times greater than that of the metal. Before and after the absorbance measurements the *pH* of the solution was measured.

Calculation :

1. *Spectrophotometry :* The method proposed by Newman and Hume^{1,2} is applied to the calculation of the formation constant of the mixed-ligand complex. This method is a highly generalised method, applicable to nearly all the systems, but very much complicated. The treatment gets much simplified when only one mixed-ligand complex is formed as in the case of a metal like copper with two bidentate ligands.

When the concentrations of the two ligands is maintained very high compared to Cu(II), it can be safely assumed that the higher complex, binary or ternary would be present at all times. Then

$$\bar{A} = \epsilon_{CuA_2}[CuA_2] + \epsilon_{CuAB}[CuAB] + \epsilon_{CuB_2}[CuB_2] \dots (1)$$

For the equilibrium

$$K_{form} = \frac{[CuBA][B]}{[CuB_2][A]} \dots (3)$$

and for the equilibrium

$$K_{repl} = \frac{[CuA_2][B]}{[CuBA][A]} \dots (5)$$

with high concentration of only one ligand, e.g. A, CuA₂ would be present and the ϵ_{CuA_2} can be calculated.

$$A_0 = \epsilon_{CuA_2}[Cu(II)] \dots (6)$$

When A > B then only CuA₂ and CuAB will be present under favourable pH conditions. Then,

$$\bar{A} = K_{repl} \left\{ (A_0 - \bar{A}) \frac{A}{B} \right\} + \epsilon_{CuAB}[Cu(II)] \dots (7)$$

A plot of \bar{A} vs $(A_0 - \bar{A}) \frac{A}{B}$ yields a straight line with K_{repl} as slope and from the intercept ϵ_{CuAB} can be calculated.

When A/B ratio is appreciable all the 3 species, CuA₂, CuAB and CuB₂ will be present and if a wavelength is so chosen that only CuA₂ and CuAB species absorb, then,

$$\begin{aligned} & [(K_{repl} (A_0 - \bar{A}) A/B) - \bar{A}] \\ & = 1/K_{form} \{ \bar{A} \times B/A \} - \epsilon_{CuAB}[Cu(II)] \dots (8) \end{aligned}$$

Here a plot of the terms in the left-hand side vs the brace-enclosed terms yields a straight line with $1/K_{form}$ as slope and from the intercept ϵ_{CuAB} can be calculated. This permits a check on the value of ϵ_{CuAB} .

2. *pH-metry :* The following species were taken into account in the computation of the formation constant of the mixed-ligand complex HA, A, H₂B, HB, B, CuA, CuA₂, CuB, CuB₂, CuAB and Cu. Here HA and H₂B represent lactic acid and protonated amino acid respectively. Charges are not included for convenience. The method of calculation used is that of Nasanen and Koskinen^{10,11} with slight modification.

Results and Discussion

The extent to which a mixed-ligand complex is favoured in formation is better expressed by terms such as $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ than by $\log \beta_{CuAB}$. $\log X$ can be obtained by considering a "disproportionation" reaction shown below,

$$X = \frac{[CuAB]^2}{[CuA_2][CuB_2]} \dots (10)$$

$$\log X = 2 \log \beta_{CuAB} - (\log \beta_{CuA_2} + \log \beta_{CuB_2}) \dots (11)$$

The value of $\log X$ calculated on statistical basis only is 0.6¹³. Here an experimentally determined value of $\log X = 0.6$ or more clearly indicates the favoured formation of the mixed-ligand complex. $\Delta \log K$ is derived from 1 : 1 binary complexes while $\log X$ is derived from 1 : 2 binary complexes.

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{CuAB} - \log K_{CuB} \dots (14)$$

From statistical considerations, the most appropriate value for $\Delta \log K$ has been proposed to be -0.9 ¹⁴ for a distorted octahedral complex of Cu(II) with bidentate ligands. Hence an experimentally determined value of $\Delta \log K = -0.9$ or more indicates favoured formation of the mixed-ligand complex.

In the pH-metric method the concentration of the ligand used is comparable to that of the metal ion. While in the spectrophotometric method it is kept very manyfold greater since no free metal ion should be present. Hence it is appropriate to calculate $\Delta \log K$ from the results obtained from pH metric studies and $\log X$ from the spectrophotometric studies.

$\log \beta_{CuAB}$ and $\Delta \log K$ values for the copper-lactate-aminocarboxylate complexes are given in Table 1. Titrations with varying concentrations of

the two ligands show no indication of the formation of complex species other than [Cu lact am].*

TABLE 1— $\log \beta_{[\text{Cu lact L}]}$ AND $\Delta \log K$ VALUES FOR THE MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ AND AT $\mu = 0.25$ (KNO_3) OBTAINED BY pH METRIC METHOD

Sl. No.	L	$\log \beta_{[\text{Cu lact L}]}$	$\Delta \log K$
1.	glycinate	10.91	+0.16
2.	α -alaninate	10.65	-0.04
3.	serinate	10.02	-0.03
4.	β -alaninate	9.97	+0.38

For all the systems the $\Delta \log K$ value is much higher than that predicted on statistical grounds. This shows the highly favoured formation of these mixed complexes. This is further confirmed by the $\log X$ values obtained from the spectrophotometric studies.

At 900 nm, the molar absorptivity of $\text{Cu}(\text{lact})_2$ is very high compared to that of the $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$. When the ratio of lact/gly is maintained very high and at $\text{pH} > 5.0$ only $\text{Cu}(\text{lact})_2$ and [Cu lact gly] are the species present, then eq. (7) is applicable. From a plot using this equation the value of K_{repl} obtained is 1.527×10^{-7} and $\epsilon_{[\text{Cu lact gly}]}$ is 21.8. If the ratio of lact/gly is maintained at a moderate level and the pH between 5 and 6, all the three species, $\text{Cu}(\text{lact})_2$ and [Cu lact gly] and $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$ are present. But at 900 nm $\text{Cu}(\text{lact})_2$ and [Cu lact gly] absorb appreciably and then eq. (8) is applicable. Using this equation the value of K_{form} obtained is 3.00×10^{-5} and $\epsilon_{[\text{Cu lact gly}]}$ is 21.5. In both cases the value of $\epsilon_{[\text{Cu lact gly}]}$ obtained is very nearly the same. This confirms the validity of the assumptions made. The overall formation constant of the mixed-ligand complex is calculated from both K_{repl} and K_{form} . The average of the value of $\log \beta_{\text{CuAB}}$ obtained and $\log X$ values calculated are given in Table 2. The $\log \beta_{\text{CuAB}}$ values obtained by spectrophotometric method agree well with those obtained by pH-metry.

TABLE 2— $\log \beta_{[\text{Cu lact L}]}$ AND $\log X$ VALUES FOR THE MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ AND AT $\mu = 0.25$ (KNO_3) OBTAINED BY SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD

Sl. No.	L	$\log \beta_{[\text{Cu lact L}]}$	$\log X$
1.	glycinate	10.74	2.33
2.	α -alaninate	10.22	1.56
3.	serinate	9.76	1.53
4.	β -alaninate	9.69	2.71

Four factors appear to be significant in determining the relative stabilities of the mixed-ligand complexes. They are, nature of the donor atoms, ring sizes, neutralisation of charge and steric effect.

* abbreviations: ala= α -alaninate, bala= β -alaninate, am=aminocarboxylate, bipy=2,2'-bipyridyl, en=ethylenediamine, gly=glycinate, glyK=glycollate, lact=lactate, mal=malonate, ox=oxalate, pn=1,3-propylenediamine, sal=salicylate and ser=serinate.

In [Cu lact am] complexes copper is co-ordinated to three oxygen atoms and one N atom. The $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ values are higher than for those containing only nitrogen or only oxygen as the donor atoms as can be seen from Table 3. The indication is that copper prefers mixed donors for complexation rather than homo donors.

TABLE 3— $\Delta \log K$ AND/OR $\log X$ VALUES OF SOME MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II)

Sl. No.	Mixed-ligand Complex	$\Delta \log K$	$\log X$	Ref.
1.	[Cu ox mal]	—	0.92	15
2.	[Cu lact gly]	+0.16	2.33	This work
3.	[Cu lact ala]	-0.04	1.56	This work
4.	[Cu lact ser]	-0.03	1.53	This work
5.	[Cu lact bala]	+0.38	2.71	This work
6.	[Cu glyK gly]	-0.48	—	5
7.	[Cu sal ala]	—	2.63	16
8.	[Cu sal ser]	—	1.76	16
9.	[Cu bipy glyK]	-0.10	—	6
10.	[Cu ox en]	—	0.94	2
11.	[Cu ox pn]	—	3.14	2
12.	[Cu bipy en]	—	1.10	2

$\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ values for [Cu lact bala] are greater than those for the copper-lactate- α -aminocarboxylate systems. This indicates that copper mixed-ligand complexes having a five- and a six-membered ring in the same complex is preferred over those containing two five-membered rings. Examples given in Table 3, confirm this.

The 1 : 1 binary complexes of copper-lactate and copper-aminocarboxylate carry a +1 charge. The mixed-ligand complex is neutral. The formation of a neutral species appears to be a strong driving force for the favoured formation of the mixed-ligand complex. This may be one of the reasons for the enhanced value of $\Delta \log K$.

Eventhough the co-ordination tendency of the un-ionized hydroxyl group in lactic acid is weak, it is sufficient enough for the acid to function as a bidentate ligand. This is evident from the binary formation constants. In mixed-ligand complexes also, hydroxyl group participation in co-ordination is known^{6,9}. Because of the weak co-ordination of the hydroxyl group in $\text{Cu}(\text{lact})_2$ it prefers a stronger chelating ligand like glycine. Thus glycine preferentially replaces one lactate group to form [Cu lact gly]. The low pH and the low concentration of the glycinate ion do not favour much the formation of the $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$. This explains why the mixed-ligand complex formation is favoured and the observed $\log X$ value is higher.

In the case of the mixed-ligand complexes formed by α -amino acids, the $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ values are the greatest for glycinate, α -alaninate comes next and serinate last. This trend may be attributed to steric factors.

The distribution of various species present in a particular system as a % of the total copper concentration and their variation with the pH of the solution gives a good idea of the favoured formation of mixed-ligand complexes as also pH effects. As a representative system [Cu lact gly] is presented in Fig. 1. Here the concentration of [Cu lact gly]

Fig. 1. The distribution of various species as a function of pH.
Curve : 1. Cu^{2+} , 2. [Cu lact], 3. [Cu lact gly],
4. [Cu gly], 5. $[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2]$.

increases with pH. At 4.80 pH it reaches 55% of total copper. At low pH [Cu lact] complex is the major species present. As pH increases the concentration of $\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2$ species start rising. This is

expected from the ionisation constants of the two ligands.

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